
Awareness and Use of Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) in University Libraries: A Review

Irfanullah

Research Scholar, Department of Library and Information Sciences
Central University of Punjab, Bathinda, 151401
Email: irfanahmadamu4351@gmail.com

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted on: 21-02-2025

Published on: 14-03-2025

Keywords:

OPAC, Web OPAC, University libraries, frequency and satisfaction

ABSTRACT

The current study outlines the review of related literature on Awareness and Use of OPAC, web OPAC and card catalogues in University Libraries all over the world and incorporates awareness and use, how users learn, how frequently OPAC is utilised, its purposes, different search strategy, problems encountered in the use of OPAC, degree of satisfaction and various suggestions for the betterment of OPAC and to maximize the use of various facilities in the library. Keeping in view few national and international levels of similar studies have been evaluated for the same.

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15026934>

Introduction

Textbooks, theses, manuscripts, magazines, publications, maps, movies, tapes, and other published and unpublished resources are all arranged properly in a place called a library. It contains the knowledge base that is disseminated via channels of information. Catalogues are useful resources for retrieval of documents. OPAC is a supplement of the printed catalogue in its digital format and serves a variety of purposes. This additionally acts as a guide for those looking for specific records. Similar to a gateway, the library OPAC functions as the main page for the library website. Using the most recent mechanism, information is made public frequently. Users may find documents using keywords, authors, titles, and subjects using a computer. Materials are also capable of being printed, downloaded, or exported using various technological devices. Utilizing the interlibrary loan feature offered by the OPAC, certain

libraries permit users to ask for materials across a different library. The ALA Glossary of Library and Information Science (1983) defines OPAC as a computer-based and supported library catalogue. It is designed to be accessible via terminals, so that library users may directly and effectively search and retrieve bibliographic records without the assistance of a human intermediary. Before beginning to write research at any stage, a review of the literature is necessary since it is a fundamental assignment that is expected to be completed carefully and is included in all studies and academic articles. It aids the scholar in gaining a broad understanding of his subject matter. The present piece of review includes, a few Indian and foreign levels of these studies have been evaluated.

OPAC Awareness and Use

The investigator explored the study in five libraries in Delhi and found that 56% users were utilising the OPAC services provided by these libraries (Ansari and Amita, 2008). Majorities (74%) of the respondents in University of Ilorin, Nigeria were aware about OPAC and using it for searching the required documents (Adedibu, 2008). Rajput, Naidu and Jadon (2008) showed in their study that most (83.79%) of participants in Devi Ahilya University Library Indore were using OPAC services accommodated by the library. Researchers of the survey at libraries of engineering colleges in Karnataka pointed that (81.61%) were using OPAC for retrieving documents (Mulla and Chandrashekara, 2009). Similar kind of research conducted by Kumar and Vohra (2011) in at GNDU Library, Amritsar and identified that awareness of OPAC (93.3%) among users were very high. A comparative study in three universities in Punjab showed high awareness of OPAC (Kumar and Vohra, 2011). Madhusudhan (2012) explored that when foreign students started attending the University of Delhi, a large number of international students from underdeveloped nations hadn't utilized Web-OPAC because they were unaware of the resources connected with OPAC. A study in Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar found that 73.7% users were aware and use both OPAC and Card catalogue (Narang & Singh, 2013). Fabunmi and Asubiojo (2013) examined the study in Obafemi Awolowo University, Nigeria showed that 68.7 % respondents were aware of OPAC facilities. Study carried out among students in two universities, Nigeria showed that majority of the respondents did not use OPAC facility (Onuoha, Umahi and Bamidele, 2013). It was seen that users possessed a good understanding of OPAC in both University libraries but its use not up to their level of understanding (Fati and Adetimirin, 2015). A survey was conducted by Msagati (2016) in Open University of Tanzania revealed poor consciousness (24.78 %) of OPAC. More than half (59.09%) users in PEC University of Technology, Chandigarh were utilising OPAC facility (Vasishta and Dhingra, 2017). In the same vein Saha (2017) investigated in 17 libraries at

KIIT University and found that most (95.05%) of the participants were very much aware and using OPAC.

Kumar et al. (2018) reviewed more than sixty national & international papers found that majority of patrons were aware of OPAC and utilising it to fulfill their educational requirement. A study among UG students in Federal University Libraries in Northern Nigeria showed that most of the patrons had significant knowledge of OPAC with mean=3.22 but they were less significant in use of OPAC (Song, Buba & Song 2018). Rout and Panigrahi (2018) observed that awareness of OPAC (71.32%) among the library users in Odisha was very impressive. Study carried out in university libraries of Haryana mentioned that majority (86%) of participants were aware of OPAC and using it freely (Kumar, 2019). Significant number (77%) of library users knew about OPAC and making good use of this service in the library premises (Kumar and Singh, 2019). Study carried by Igbudu and Ver (2020) at Benue State University Library in Nigeria obtained the result that majority (60.4%) of the library users were not aware of OPAC facility provided by the library. The investigator conducted the study in University of Ilorin, Nigeria pointed good awareness of OPAC among the respondents (Bashorun and Akorede, 2020). Finding of the research in University of Agricultural Sciences, Karnataka indicated that 79.66% of the faculties were aware and using OPAC (Uplaonkar, 2020). Krishnappa and Kemparaju (2020) obtained that great number (80.34%) of users in Dr. V.K.R.V Rao library, ISEC, Bangalore were aware of OPAC and utilising it in their research work. Comparative study carried out in two colleges of Assam experienced good awareness (75%) of OPAC (Sharma, 2020). Aju and Tofi (2020) highlighted that majority of the respondents at University libraries in Nasarawa State, Nigeria were aware of OPAC with mean=3.54% and making good use of this service. In the same pattern Isah (2023) carried out the study at Bayero University Library Nigeria figured that 86.21% were aware of OPAC. Research conducted at Catholic University College of Ghana figure out good awareness (68.5%) about OPAC among library users (Adjei et al., 2024).

OPAC Learning

Majority of the Participants learned how to use OPAC through training (50.27%) followed by conferences/seminars (35.16%) organised by university (Rajput, Naidu, Jadon, 2008). Mulla and Chandrashekara (2009) found most of the time (40.02%) library users were assisted by library staff in need. Finding depicted the need of assistanceship from the library staff for better utilisation of OPAC in the library (Kumar and Vohra, 2011). Kumar (2012) observed that large number of respondents either

assisted by library staff or taken help of their colleague and remaining quit the search process at the moment. Foreign students from under developed countries in University of Delhi figure out that they took the benefits of their friends (55%) in using Web OPAC facility offered by the library (Madhusudhan, 2012). Result of the study at the library of Unnamalai Institute of Technology in Kovilpatti revealed that 36.96% users were assisted by library staff in using OPAC services (Sankari et al., 2013). In the same vein Narang and Singh (2013) revealed that majority (36.5%) of the researchers in GNDU, Amritsar took help from their friends for learning OPAC. User either request for support from their friend (39.02%) or took the benefit of other user of OPAC (31.71%) near the terminal (Adenike and Akin, 2013). Finding of the study investigated in Open University of Tanzania indicated that 45.65% & 46.52% received the support of their colleagues and assistanceship of library staff respectively (Msagati, 2016). Similar result was obtained by Kumar (2019) that majority (27%) of patrons was helped by library staff in using OPAC. Major supports (21.9%) in using OPAC were observed from the staff member in all four university libraries in Haryana (Kumar and Singh, 2019). Less than half (48%) of the users learnt OPAC to use by the instructions given at terminals (Sharma, 2020).

Frequency of Use

OPAC was occasionally (43.6%) used by science students in University of Ilorin library, Nigeria (Adedibu, 2008). Study conducted by Ansari and Amita (2008) in five libraries in Delhi figure out that (55%) of the respondents used the services of library daily. Nearly half (45.32%) of the library visitors were daily users of OPAC (Rajput, Naidu, Jadon, 2008). Similar finding were observed by Mulla and Chandrashekara (2009) that most (64.01%) of the users were accessing OPAC on daily basis. The patrons of the two chosen University Libraries in Lagos State, Nigeria very Often (49.45%) used OPAC (Adigun et al., 2011). Islam and Ahmed (2011) indicated that majority of students in Dhaka University Bangladesh used OPAC minimum one time in a month. Most of the users (32.2%) in GNDU Library, Amritsar were utilising OPAC occasionally (Kumar and Vohra, 2011). Similar result was indicated by Kumar (2012) at Punjabi University Library, Patiala where he pointed that patrons used OPAC regularly (52%) while (34.6%) occasionally. Finding of the study in University of Delhi pointed that (40%) foreign students used Web OPAC 2-3 times in a week (Madhusudhan, 2012). Study explored by Gohain and Saikia (2013) in Tezpur University Library found that (51.03%) users were daily user of OPAC. Result of the study in GNDU, Amritsar showed that (40.1%) of the respondents used OPAC occasionally (Narang & Singh, 2013). A survey examined by Sankari et al. (2013) at the library of

Unnamalai Institute of Technology in Kovilpatti indicated that 39.23% participants used OPAC on daily basis. The finding of the study obtained that maximum numbers (56.89%) of users were daily users of OPAC (Veena, Mallaiah and Pushpalatha, 2015). Msagati (2016) found that Students in Open University Tanzania utilised OPAC services occasionally (55.77%). Interesting result was observed about the frequency of OPAC usage in government college library in Karnataka that users rarely used (33.34%) to get their required documents (Siddagangaiah and Muthuraja, 2017). Kumar and Singh (2017) explored that most of the PG students, research scholars and faculty members in GGIPU, Delhi were daily (39.0%) users of OPAC. Respondents at KIIT University very frequently (80%) visit library and used OPAC (Saha, 2017). Less than half (45.45 %) of the participants used library services 2-3 times in a week (Vasishta and Dhingra, 2017). More than half (55.20%) of the participants were daily users of OPAC (Swaminathan, 2017).

Thanuskodi (2018) found that most of the library visitors were either frequent user (31.35%) or occasionally (25.38%) user of OPAC. Majority (54.24%) of the library users in Odisha utilise OPAC only in need (Rout and Panigrahi, 2018). Study explored at the library of Jeppiaar Maamallan Engineering College in Chennai revealed that (45.84%) of the faculties used OPAC at least one time in a week (Krishnamoorthy and Muthusamy, 2018). As mentioned in the study that users make use of OPAC at least one time per day (45.46%) for retrieving documents (Kumar and Manasa, 2018). Kasimani and Rajendran (2019) studied at Public Libraries in Chennai indicated that majority (41.11%) of library visitors were taking the benefits of OPAC on weekly basis. More than half (52.4%) of the participants were daily users of OPAC (Kumar, 2019). Similarly, Beneficiaries of OPAC utilised it on daily, weekly and biweekly basis as per their requirements (Kumar and Singh, 2019). Interestingly about half (47.5%) of the participants in university libraries in south-Nigeria rarely used OPAC services which indicates low awareness among students (Eserada and Okolo, 2019). Users of OPAC facility used it once a week (28.21%) in Dr. V.K.R.V Rao library, ISEC, Bangalore (Krishnappa and Kemparaju, 2020). Uplaonkar (2020) showed that majority (35.59%) of the faculty members were daily users of OPAC. Respondents from both colleges in Assam used OPAC at least (39%) once in a week (Sharma, 2020). According to the data that (38.5%) respondents were daily users of OPAC (Adegun et al., 2021). Participants occasionally (78.75%) used OPAC (Isah, 2023).

Purposes of using OPAC

Adedibu (2008) in their study revealed that consulting library books and journals for assignments (29.64%) was the main purpose of the respondents for using OPAC. Large number of (61.81%) of participants visit library and used OPAC to find out whether the study materials were available or not in the library (Rajput, Naidu, Jadon, 2008). Survey of the research revealed that 31% users visit the library to know the latest arrivals of the study material in the library while 30% used library as a means of peaceful place for study (Ansari and Amita, 2008). Mulla and Chandrashekara (2009) in their research indicated that OPAC was basically used by users to know the exact location of documents (90.29%) followed by availability of desired books (73.63%) in the library. Good numbers of patrons (63.2%) at GNDU library, Amritsar were using OPAC to know the availability of the desired documents (Kumar and Vohra, 2011). Kumar and Vohra (2011) indicated cumulative purpose in three libraries for utilising OPAC were found to be (72.1%) as to make sure the availability of the needed documents. Result of the survey indicated that majority of the foreign students (55%) in University of Delhi utilised the benefits of Web OPAC for the purpose of finding book titles (Madhusudhan, 2012). Most of the respondents (52.05%) in Tezpur University Library used OPAC for locating document on shelves (Gohain & Saikia, 2013). It was found in the study that 46.1% used OPAC for pinpoint books in the library (Narang & Singh, 2013). More than half (57.69%) of the users utilised OPAC to find out the availability of needed documents (Sankari et al., 2013). Veena, Mallaiah and Pushpalatha (2015) explored main reason of using OPAC and quantified as users find out the correct location of the documents (36.22%). Most of OPAC users use it to identify exact location (34.18%) and know availability (32.49%) of the documents (SI and Priyanwada, 2016). Users in GGIPU, Delhi utilized OPAC for getting bibliographical details (32.4%) or to identify the location (30.7%) of the documents in the library (Kumar and Singh, 2017). Vasishta and Dhingra (2017) noticed in their study that checking the availability of the desired books (63.7 %) whereas locating of the study materials (54.54%) were major searches through OPAC.

To check new entry of documents (79.6%) was observed by most of the respondents as the chief reason of using OPAC in Anna University Regional Campus, Coimbatore (Swaminathan, 2017). To identify the status of issue and return of the books (44.45%) accompanied by (42.22%) to know the availability of study materials in the library were found to be main purposes of the respondents (Siddagangaiah and Muthuraja, 2017). Kumar and Manasa (2018) identified creating list of titles on specific themes (36.36%) were stated as chief purpose for utilising OPAC. Rout and Panigrahi (2018) found main purpose of using OPAC as checking whether the required documents (73.56%) were

available or not in the library (2018). Similar finding was obtained by Thanuskodi (2018) which showed great numbers (74.03%) of the library visitors make use of OPAC to check the availability of desired study material in the library. In the same vein finding indicated that (29.17%) of the faculty members used OPAC service to know the existence of documents in the library (Krishnamoorthy and Muthusamy, 2018). Similarly among all purposes user of OPAC searched to know the availability of the study materials (36.67%) in the library (Kasimani and Rajendran, 2019). Main purpose as stated by most (35.3%) of the patrons was to know whether the documents were available or not in the library (Kumar, 2019). Lots of users (29.5%) take OPAC services to obtain information about availability of needed documents (Kumar and Singh, 2019). High percentage of users (Mean=4.1) utilise OPAC facility to know the exact location of the documents in the library (Eserada and Okolo, 2019). Krishnappa and Kemparaju, (2020) identified major reasons of using OPAC in ISEC, Bangalore was to know the status of current journal (81.2%) followed by exact location of books (77.78%) in the library. Same result was obtained in their study by Uplaonkar (2000) & Sharma (2020) that majority (72.88%) of the faculty members and (32%) respondents used OPAC to know whether books/journals were available or not in the library respectively. According to the data examined in Olusegun Oke Library, Nigeria most of the users (33.1%) utilise the OPAC to locate journals as well as additional documents to read (Adegun et al., 2021).

OPAC Search Strategies

Most of the participants searched study material by name of the author (51%) in order to fulfill their need (Ansari and Amita, 2008). Similar results were observed in the study investigated by Wanigasooriya (2008) in which most searched option were accessed as title (26.83%) accompanied by subject (26.39%) of the required documents. Author (36.37%) and title (35.16%) were found to be most preferred searched points for accessing required documents (Rajput, Naidu, Jadon, 2008). Large numbers (46.3%) of the users browse their needed documents through subject (Adedibu, 2008). Surveyor of study showed in their result that most of the users searched through author of the documents (96.7%) while (92.67%) through title of the works (Mulla and Chandrashekara, 2009). Kumar and Vohra (2011) found majority of the respondents retrieved their desired documents by title of the documents (50%) whereas (48.5%) by name of the author. A comparative study in IIT Delhi, IIT Kanpur and Kashmir University explored that most of the respondents simply searched through title of documents (Ahmad, Mushtaq and Imran, 2012). Foreign students in University of Delhi searched their research materials through title (68%) of the documents (Madhusudhan, 2012). In the same vein Arshad

and Shafique (2012) indicated title of documents (81.6%) followed by name of author (50%) were most preferred search choice in Punjab University Library, Pakistan. The ability of the participants to find information was found quite poor (Fabunmi and Asubiojo, 2013). User of OPAC retrieved their required materials by searching through author (95.38%) followed by title (91.54%) of the documents (Sankari et al., 2013). Narang and Singh (2013) obtained author (43.2%) & Title (37.4%) as the main key words searched for obtaining the study materials. As mentioned in the finding patrons accessed OPAC to retrieve the reading materials through name of the author (37.07%) followed by title (28.44%) of the work (Veena, Mallaiah and Pushpalatha, 2015).

More than one third (37%) of the respondents (especially staff and faculty members) used OPAC through author search for their desire documents (SI and Priyanwada, 2016). Similarly Siddagangaiah and Muthuraja (2017) pointed title search (50%) as most frequent used option. Most search approach identified as title of works (54.54%) followed by name of the author (53.41%) and (47.16%) by key word (Vasishta and Dhingra, 2017). Faculties (57.9%) and students (61.21%) searched to retrieve documents through title of the works (Swaminathan, 2017). Krishnamoorthy and Muthusamy (2018) showed almost all access points were utilised by same number of time. Most preferred approach of accessing OPAC to get the documents were subject approach (63.34%) and (58.89%) by author's approach (Kasimani and Rajendran, 2019). More than half (55.1%) of the participants used the title for searching needed study materials (Bashorun and Akorede, 2019). Uplaonkar (2020) noticed Title (79.66%) & Author (72.88%) were most utilised access points for getting their documents. Respondents in ISEC, Bangalore searched their required study material by Title of work (66.67%) followed by (64.10%) name of the author (Krishnappa and Kemparaju, 2020). Sharma (2020) identified in their work that author was mostly preferred search terminal in finding the documents in both college's libraries.

Problems Faced by users in the Use of OPAC

Poor assistanceship provided by the library staff (37.08%) and inadequate numbers of computes (30.21%) were found major obstacles in better utilisation of OPAC (Rajput, Naidu, Jadon, 2008). Lack of terminals and less efficient OPAC Module were the major problems felt by the users of two chosen University Libraries in Lagos State, Nigeria (Adigun et al., 2011). Kumar and Vohra (2011) noticed half (50%) of the participants and Kumar (2012) obtained most of the users in Punjabi University Library, Patiala faced same difficulties in the use of OPAC. Majority of the foreign students (76%) in University of Delhi found language as a barrier in utilising Web OPAC (Madhusudhan, 2012). Study examined by

Gohain and Saikia (2013) in Tezpur University Library found that users were inefficient (52.82%) in using OPAC. Large number (74.6%) of the respondents in GNDU, Amritsar did not face any problem in consulting or using OPAC (Narang & Singh, 2013). Majority of the users cited network outages, erratic electrical supplies, and a lack of computer equipment assigned to OPAC as barriers to OPAC utilization (Fabunmi and Asubiojo, 2013). Onuoha, Umahi and Bamidele (2013) figure out Shortage of systems, low level of electric supply and no provision for orientation programme for increasing literacy of OPAC among the students were some major obstacles. Less awareness (35.34%) and inadequate ability among patrons (31.89%) were big challenge for the users of OPAC (Veena, Mallaiah and Pushpalatha, 2015). Slow speed of internet (68.26%), restricted system access (70.87%), and poor browsing abilities (73.91%) were discovered major difficulties in Open University Tanzania (Msagati, 2016). Mole and Mesagan (2017) explored their study in three universities libraries in Nigeria found inadequate number of computers; irregular power supply and system break down were challenges in better utilisation of OPAC. Unavailability of link to digital material (44.88%) and urgent need for training (40.9%) were identified as big challenges (Vasishta and Dhingra, 2017).

Lower level of awareness of OPAC (24.73%) and inadequate number of access points (19.23%) were found to be big hurdles in better utilization of OPAC in GGIPU, Delhi (Kumar and Singh, 2017). Siddagangaiah and Muthuraja (2017) found greater than half (65.56%) of the users faced difficulty as no assistance was given by the library staff in time. Many obstacles were observed related shortage of computer, absence of library guide for OPAC and lack of assistance from library staff (Song, Buba & Song 2018). In the pace Rout and Panigrahi (2018) identified as query was not framed properly (84.64%) & slow response rate or failure (71.9%) as the major hurdles in better utilisation of OPAC. Majority of library visitors did not know how to use (95%) while (70%) were very much confused about searching through OPAC (Thanuskodi, 2018). Slow band width of internet (46.67%) were found big problem in steady use of OPAC (Kasimani and Rajendran, 2019). Kumar (2019) noticed need for assistance from library staffs (25.4%) were observed as big challenge for OPAC users. Less number of computers for OPAC and low assistanceship from library staff were major hurdles in better utilisation of this service (Kumar and Singh, 2019). Eserada and Okolo (2019) obtained in their finding as unavailability of electricity in need and poor awareness was big challenge. It was interesting point noted in the result that use of OPAC was the big challenge for the respondents as (67.52%) had not enough time to utilise it (Krishnappa and Kemparaju, 2020). Sharma (2020) clarified that displacement of the study materials on the shelves by users and result shown through OPAC search was not matching,

that was a big challenge of all problems in both libraries. Major problems were either insufficient guidance about utilizing OPAC or OPAC was not operating correctly (Adegun et al., 2021). Lack of information technology expertise among students with mean =3.55 was found to be a big hurdle in better utilisation of OPAC (Adjei et al., 2024).

Users degree of Satisfaction regarding OPAC

Ansari and Amita (2008) revealed in the survey that participants were either fully satisfied or satisfied with the facilities offered by the libraries. Majority of the respondents were found to be happy with the services available for the users of the library (Mulla and Chandrashekara, 2009). Less than half (45.6%) of the respondents were slightly satisfied with the usage of OPAC (Kumar and Vohra, 2011). Similarly, most of the respondents were very satisfied with the services offered by the library (Gohain & Saikia, 2013). More than half (62.8%) of the users were satisfied with the assistanceship provided by library staff and (57.2%) were not satisfied with the number of computer available for accessing OPAC (Narang & Singh, 2013). Onuoha, Umahi and Bamidele (2013) indicated large numbers of respondents in two universities, Nigeria were moderately satisfied with over all library's services although they were not much utilising OPAC. (Half (50%) of the respondents were satisfied followed by (19.23%) fully satisfied with OPAC facility (Sankari et al., 2013). Msagati (2016) noticed that majority of the students in Open University Tanzania were satisfied with services provided by the library. Patrons of OPAC in GGIPU, Delhi were found to be satisfied (54.4%) with the OPAC facility (Kumar and Singh, 2017). Healthy numbers (68.19%) of users were satisfied (Vasishta and Dhingra, 2017). Swaminathan (2017) explored that majority of faculty member and students either fully satisfied or satisfied with OPAC services offered by the library. Heavy numbers (91.11%) of respondents were found neither satisfied nor dissatisfied (Siddagangaiah and Muthuraja, 2017).

Thanuskodi (2018) observed in the research that most of the library visitors were either fully satisfied or simply satisfied with OPAC and other facilities provided by the library. Similarly, more than half (54.16%) of the faculty member were fully satisfied while (25%) satisfied (Krishnamoorthy and Muthusamy, 2018). Kumar and Manasa (2018) indicated nearly half (48.18%) of the user stated good level of satisfaction. More than half (58.89%) of respondents were found to be satisfied with OPAC services (Kasimani and Rajendran, 2019). In the same pace Kumar (2019) admitted in their study most (43.9%) of the respondents were found to be satisfied with overall facilities offered by library. Level of satisfaction was found to be satisfactory (37.8%) in all libraries covered in the study (Kumar and Singh,

2019). Maximum numbers of the library users were either satisfied or moderately satisfied with facilities offered by the library (Bashorun and Akorede, 2020). Uplaonkar (2020) showed high percentage (79.66%) of the faculty member found to be satisfied with library staff and OPAC services. Most of (46.15%) the respondents in ISEC, Bangalore were highly satisfied with the OPAC facility (Krishnappa and Kemparaju, 2020). Healthy numbers (71.5%) of the users were found to be satisfied with OPAC facility in both libraries in Assam (Sharma, 2020). Igbudu and Ver (2020) identified maximum users as dissatisfied of OPAC services. Finding revealed majority of users were dissatisfied with OPAC services (Aju and Tofi, 2020). In totality large numbers of respondents (89.2%) were satisfied while using OPAC (Adegun et al., 2021).

Recommendations

In order to accommodate multiple visitors at once, initiatives need to be taken to guarantee that the library should purchase additional modern systems for employees as well as for learners. Adedibu (2008) recommended looking into the power supply problem. According to an evaluation on Delhi's libraries, retraining is essential towards effectively employing technologies (Ansari and Amita, 2008). The study suggested putting the OPAC adjacent to shelves and organizing the publication's indexing in a methodical manner (Rajput, Naidu, Jadon, 2008). Adigun et al. (2011) advised to better serve existing and future clientele, librarians ought to adopt the initiative and pursue self-improvement by utilizing learning and retraining programme and plan for additional OPAC systems that must be situated nearer to the section with the book stacks. Proper guidance from library staff should be provided to patrons in order to maximize the use of OPAC facility (Kumar and Vohra 2011). Employees at the library must come forward to help patrons in browsing OPAC for traditional materials (Arshad and Shafique, 2012). Kumar (2012) mentioned authority must address user's issues and prioritize creating a suitable OPAC infrastructure while taking into account their preferences in the era of technology. Linkages to digital resources, easier way to use online assistance, and user training initiatives were suggested to be addressed (Thanuskodi, 2012). The investigator recommended for specialized training in various languages for using DULS Web-OPAC effectively (Madhusudhan, 2012). At the commencement of every academic term, the library ought to organize an event to raise awareness and more devices need to be installed for better utilisation of OPAC (Gohain and Saikia, 2013). Narang and Singh (2013) suggested in order helping visitors, employee should be assigned close to the systems and simple instructions on how to navigate the OPAC has to be posted next to the computer or announcement boards. Enough devices should be placed to enable learners for accessing materials at the OPAC, and the

library should have an additional electricity source to guarantee a constant supply of electricity (Adenike and Akin, 2013). To provide superior facilities for its patrons, the nation's libraries need to rebuild and modernize existing electronic networks and technological devices (Sankari et al., 2013). The investigators advised for delivering efficient instruction on how to conduct searches for pertinent data and add additional systems for optimal utilisation of OPAC (Fabunmi and Asubiojo, 2013). Fati and Adetimirin (2015) mentioned lectures and practices have to be scheduled to educate them to operate OPAC effectively. The study suggested for upgradation of the principal library's information technology system, a backup power source, more OPAC devices, and better internet facilities in Tanzania (Msagati, 2016). LI and Wanigasooriya (2016) stated efforts to raise consciousness about OPAC and browsing in the native language ought to be rendered in Sri Lanka. Library staff should help patrons for more understanding on how to use OPAC (Siddagangaiah and Muthuraja, 2017). The library should regularly organize educational programs on efficient methods and approaches for retrieving information via OPAC (Vasishta and Dhingra, 2017).

The university library in Coimbatore should provide a Windows operating systems OPAC platform with simple search options and host user training programs (Krishnamoorthy and Muthusamy, 2018). Kumar and Manasa (2018) recommended that library patrons be given to orientation and instructional programs so that maximum benefits of OPAC facility can be availed in the campus. Not only number of OPAC devices must be increased but also Staff within the library ought to enhance their assistance that OPAC provides (Song, Buba and Song 2018). Similarly, Rout and Panigrahi (2018) pointed enough equipped professionals must be allocated who can aware users to use OPAC from any location. Frequent training sessions need to be planned to improve the successful application of the facilities provided by the libraries (Kumar, 2019). Kasimani and Rajendran (2019) in their research raise the points to increase number of system, improvement in library services as well as arrangement of feedback mechanism to identify and solve the problems. In order to promote the usage of OPAC, institutions must have the necessary supportive facilities, including a sufficient electrical supply and efficient web access (Eserada and Okolo, 2019). Better understanding campaigns to motivate learners along with a steady electrical source and adequate number of computer must be arranged to make greater usage of OPAC (Aju and Tofi, 2020). In the same pattern Bashorun and Akorede (2020) advised person at OPAC facility must help users and draw in the interest of the populations who don't often utilize the resources offered by libraries. To let patrons observe what needs to be improved, academic libraries may set up a mechanism for feedback including suggestion/complaint boxes along

with improvement in electricity & internet band width (Igbudu and Ver, 2020). Sharma (2020) pointed to increase understanding about OPAC, enhancing technology, and providing employee support for maximizing the interest as well as use of library services. Attempts to modernize the current OPAC devices in order achieve improved resource execution in the future (Krishnappa and Kemparaju, 2020). Adegun et al. (2021) suggested taking digital proficiency initiative among users and enhancement of OPAC's features were important points recommended. Steps for instructional programme for users as well as employee within the library premises should advance their ICT abilities to provide better service (Isah, 2023).

Conclusion

According to the review of related literature, academic library patron's operations have shifted substantially over the past 15 years and the majority of libraries are now designed to use online OPAC instead of conventional catalogue. The review of literature covered the methodology employed in their study as well as awareness about OPAC where researcher observed that majority knew it and applying on daily or occasionally basis for many purposes but main purpose are identified as to check the availability of documents in the library and to know the exact location of the study materials on the shelves. Researcher found that most of the users searched the required documents through title of works, by subject & by name of the author; in accessing if they need some support, took the help of their friends/colleagues or assisted by library staff in using OPAC. It is important to mention here that lot of problems noticed but big challenges are inadequate numbers of computers, low level of assistance from library staff and irregular power supply reduces the maximum utilisation of services provided by library. Instead of many obstacles identified in review of related literature level of satisfaction by most of library users are found to be high.

References

- Adedibu, L. O. (2008). Catalogue use by science students in the University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria, *Libri: International Journal of Library and Information Service*, 58(1), 58-62
- Adigun, A., Ojo, G., Salvador-Olayokun, S., Yewande, M., Abdulazeez, M., & Babatunde, O. (2011). An Assessment of Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) Utilization in Two Selected University Libraries in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Information Manager (The)*, 11(1-2), 85-90.

- Adegun, I. A., Akinola, J. O., Oyewumi, O. O., & Olusegun, A. S. (2021). Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) Among Library Users: A Case Study of Olusegun Oke Library, Lautech, Ogbomoso, Oyo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies*, 7(5), 11-18.
- Adjei, S., Agyeman, I. K., Adetsi, P., & Agyei, F. O. (2024). Usage of online public access to catalogue (OPAC) by library users in Catholic University College, Ghana. *Asian Journal of Information Science and Technology*, 14(1), 40-46.
- Ahmad, H., Mushtaq, M., & Imran, S. M. (2012). The Use of Search Strategies in OPAC: A Comparative Study of Central Library, IIT Delhi; PK Kelkar Library, IIT Kanpur and Allama Iqbal Library, Kashmir University. *International Research: Journal of Library and Information Science*, 2(2).
- Aju, D. T., & Foti, S. T. (2020). Undergraduates' awareness, utilization and satisfaction with online public access catalogue (OPAC) in public university libraries in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. *Library and information perspectives and research*, 2(1), 18-29.
- Alam Ansari, M., & Amita. (2008). Awareness and use of OPACs in five Delhi libraries. *The Electronic Library*, 26(1), 111-129.
- Ali, I., & Tariq, M. (2017). Historical development of web OPAC in Pakistan. *Pakistan Library and Information Journal*, 48(1), 41-48.
- Arshad, A., & Shafique, F. (2014). What do users prefer, card catalogue or OPAC? A study of Punjab University Library. *The Electronic Library*, 32(3), 286-295.
- Bashorun, M. T., & Akorede, S. O. (2019). Awareness and use of online public access catalogue by postgraduate students in University of Ilorin Library. *Ilorin Varsity International Journal of Library & Information Science*, 2(1/2), 114-127.
- Ebiwolate, P. B. (2010). The use of the library catalogue by undergraduate students in Niger Delta University library. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1.
- Eserada, R. E., & Okolo, S. E. (2019). Use of online public access catalogue (OPAC) in selected university libraries in South-South Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*.
- Fabunmi, O. M., & Asubiojo, B. O. (2013). Awareness and use of online public access catalogue by students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 922.

- Fati, O. I., & Adetimirin, A. (2015). OPAC awareness as a factor affecting OPAC use by undergraduates in two Nigerian libraries. *International Journal of Academic Library and Information Science*, 3(3), 72-80.
- Gohain, A., & Saikia, M. (2013). Use and users satisfaction on online public access catalogue (OPAC) services among B. Tech. students of school of engineering in Tezpur University: a survey. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 990, 1-9.
- Igbudu, M. T., & Ver, A. (2020). Undergraduates' awareness, use and satisfaction with online public access catalogue (OPAC) of Benue State University Library, Makurdi, Nigeria. *Journal of Library Services and Technologies*, 2(1), 58-68.
- Islam, M., & Zayed Ahmed, S. M. (2011). Measuring Dhaka University students' perceptions of ease-of-use and their satisfaction with University Library's online public access catalogue. *Performance Measurement and Metrics*, 12(3), 142-156.
- Kasimani, C., & Rajendran, N. (2019). Use of Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) Services in District Central Library, Chennai (Tamilnadu). *Library Philosophy and Practice*.
- Kumar, S., & Vohra, R. (2011). Use of online public access catalogue in Guru Nanak Dev University library, Amritsar: a study. *SRELS Journal of Information Management*, 48(5), 519-528.
- Kumar, S., & Vohra, R. (2013). User perception and use of OPAC: a comparison of three universities in the Punjab region of India. *The Electronic Library*, 31(1), 36-54.
- Kumar, S. (2012). Impact of internet search engines on OPAC users: A study of Punjabi University, Patiala (India). *Program*, 46(1), 56-70.
- Kumar, R., Singh, J., Singh, B., & Rana, M. K. (2018). Usability of OPAC in University Libraries: A Review. *Library Philosophy & Practice*.
- Kumar, R. (2019). Use of OPAC in central university of Haryana, Mahendragarh and Maharishi Dayanand University, Rohtak: A study. *Library Philosophy and Practice*.
- Kumar, R., & Singh, J. (2019). Usability of OPAC in the university libraries of Haryana (India). *Library Philosophy and Practice*.
- Kumar, R., & Singh, J. (2017). Use of OPAC in the University Library of GGIPU, Delhi. *Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services*, 7(1), 16-20.

- Krishnamoorthy, P., & Muthusamy, C. (2018). Usage of online public access catalogue by faculty members of Jeppiaar Maamallan engineering college: A case study. *Asian Journal of Information Science and Technology*, 8(3), 15-18.
- Krishnappa, S., & Kemparaju, T. D. (2021). Awareness and use of Online Public Access Catalogue among the Social Science Researchers at Dr. VKRV Rao Library, ISEC Bangalore: A Study. *Journal of Indian Library Association Now Available at <https://journal.ilaindia.net/>*, 56(4), 97-106.
- Li, S., & WANIGASOORIYA, P. L. (2016). An investigation and analysis of online public access catalogues (OPACs) in University Libraries in Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences*, 2(1), 28.
- Madhusudhan, M. (2012). Use of web-based online public access catalogue by the Foreign Students at the University of Delhi. *World Digital Libraries*, 5(2), 43-58.
- Msagati, N. (2017). Awareness and Use of OPAC by Distance Learners: The Case of the Open University of Tanzania. *Library Philosophy & Practice*.
- Mole, A. J. C., & Mesagan, F. O. (2017). Provision of online public access catalogs for effective utilization of library resources in three university libraries in Nigeria. *Library Collections, Acquisitions, & Technical Services*, 40(1-2), 38-45.
- Mulla, K. R., & Chandrashekara, M. (2009). A study on the effective use of online public access catalogue at the libraries of engineering colleges in Karnataka (India). *International journal of library and information science*, 1(3), 29-42.
- Mustapha, A., Muhammed, I., & Ahmad, F. I. (2023). AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION OF LIBRARY USERS TOWARDS THE USE OF ONLINE PUBLIC ACCESS CATALOGUE (OPAC) IN BAYERO UNIVERSITY, KANO, LIBRARY. *Library Philosophy & Practice*.
- Narang, A., & Singh, S. (2013). Use of Online Pubic Access Catalogue by the research scholars of Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar: A Study. *Journal of Information and Knowledge*, 191-200.
- Nikam, K. (2013). Attitudes of law university library users towards the use of OPAC/Web OPAC in Andhra Pradesh: A study. *SRELS Journal of Information Management*, 50(3), 327-335.
- Omoike, A., & Oke, T. A. (2013). Online public access catalogue [OPAC] in Nigerian libraries: a case study of the Kenneth Dike Library and university of Lagos library. *Ozean Journal of Social Sciences* 6(3), 55-65.

- Onuoha, U. D., Umahi, F. O., & Bamidele, I. A. (2013). Use and satisfaction with online public access catalogue in selected university libraries in Ogun State, Nigeria. *Information and Knowledge Management*, 3(11), 1-5.
- Rout, R., & Panigrahi, P. (2018). Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) usage patterns among the library users of Odisha: a study. *International Journal of Library & Information Science (IJLIS)*, 7(1), 28-34.
- Saha, P. (2017). Use of OPAC system by library users and its services at KIIT University: A study. "Knowledge Librarian" *An International Peer Reviewed Bilingual E-Journal of Library and Information Science*, 4(6), 176-183.
- Sankari, R. L., Chinnasamy, K., & Balasubramaniam, P. (2013). A study on the use of online public access catalogue (OPAC) by students and faculty members of Unnamalai institute of Technology in Kovilpatti (Tamil Nadu). *International Journal of Library and Information Studies*, 3(1), 17-26.
- Siddagangaiah, K. N., & Muthuraja, S. (2017). Degree of satisfaction with OPAC: A survey of undergraduate college library. *International Journal of Library and Information Studies*, 7(1), 218-224.
- Singh, R. P., Naidu, G. H. S., & Jadon, G. S. (2008). Use of online public access catalogue in Devi Ahilya University Library, Indore. *Journal of Information and Knowledge*, 55-62.
- Sharma, N. (2020). Satisfaction Level of OPAC Users: a Survey of Selected UGC Recognized College Libraries. *Library Philosophy and Practice*.
- Song, I. S., Buba, A. A., & Song, U. M. (2018). Awareness and use of Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) by undergraduate students in federal university libraries in northern Nigeria. *International Journal of Informatio and Communication Technology (ICT)*, 15(2), 75-86.
- Swaminathan, K. S. M. (2017). Use and awareness of online public access catalogue (OPAC) by Students and faculty members of Anna University Regional Campus, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu– A Case Study. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 5(5), 5345-5349.
- Thanuskodi, S. (2012). Use of online public access catalogue at Annamalai University Library. *International Journal of Information Science*, 2(6), 70-74.

- Uplaonkar, S. S. (2020). Usage and awareness of OPAC by faculty of University Library, University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwad. *Library Progress (International)*, 40(1), 87-91
- Vasishta, S., & Dhingra, N. (2017). Awareness and use of OPAC as information retrieval tool: A study of PEC University of Technology, Chandigarh, India. *International Journal of Information Dissemination and Technology*, 7(1), 19-25.
- Veena, G., Mallaiah, T. Y., & Pushpalatha, K. (2012). Use and awareness of online public access catalogue (OPAC) facility by users of SVS College Library, Bantwala, Mangalore-A study. *International Journal of Library and Information Studies*, 5(4), 65-71.
- Vijayakumar, S., & Manasa, S. (2018). Attitude of OPAC users at Regional Institute of Education, Mysore: A survey. *Journal of Library & Information Science*, 8(2), 71-98.
- Wanigasooriya, A. W. A. (2008). A Study of Problems Faced By the Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC), Users in Sri Lankan University Libraries.